

CODEN [USA]: IAJPB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**EFFICACY OF ASPIRIN IN IHD AND ITS EFFECTS ON LIVER
FUNCTIONS**¹Dr. Rafia irfan, ^{2*}Dr. Iqra javed, ³Dr. Noor Naseer¹PMDC: 103201-P., ²PMDC # 99328-P., ³CNIC # : 35202-8264151-8.**Article Received:** November 2019 **Accepted:** December 2019 **Published:** January 2020**Abstract:**

Aspirin is the prototype of NSAIDs, that is widely used as an anti aggregant for prophylaxis of ischemic heart disease (IHD), usually is given as 75 mg/d, aspirin is a non-selective COX inhibitor, as well as is the only irreversible inhibitor of COX enzymes. Aspirin is metabolized into acetic acid and salicylates. Hence aspirin can cause salicylism, in which signs and symptoms may range from mild nausea and vomiting, abdominal pain, lethargy, tinnitus, and dizziness to severe such as seizure or cerebral edema depending on the dose consumed. Although very-low-dose (mini-dose) aspirin is used increasingly as a platelet aggregation inhibitor, no studies have been published on whether aspirin's hepatic effects occur at dosages of <0.5 gm/day. The aim of the present study was to evaluate the effects of commonly used mini-dosages of aspirin on hepatic functions in elderly patients for prophylaxis of IHD. About 54 elderly patients are investigated, they were given 75mg, 150 and 325 mg, for about 5 months, CBC and hepatic tests were taken before and after treatment. The serum of blood glucose is also evaluated. The main result is that hepatic functions in patients receiving 75, or 150 mg /d still around normal ranges, but significant hepatic alterations have occurred in patients treated with 325 mg/d., as well as the incidence of hypoglycemia.

Corresponding author:**Dr. Iqra javed,**PMDC # 99328-P., Email : star920@yahoo.com

QR code

Please cite this article in press Iqra javed et al., *Efficacy Of Aspirin In Ihd And Its Effects On Liver Functions.*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2020; 07(01).

INTRODUCTION:

The research study included elderly patients (60-75 y), patients were excluded if they had hepatic or renal failures, history of bleeding, or if they were receiving anticoagulants, aspirin, or nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs. Patients are divided into 3 groups according to an antiaggregant dose of aspirin; each cluster includes 15 patients.

The first group was given 75 mg/day, The second group was given 150 mg/day, and The third group was given 325 mg/day. The investigation was for a period of 5 months.

CBC, hepatic tests (plasma proteins, triglycerides, SGPT, SGOT, ALP) and levels of sugar are assessed before administration of aspirin and every month. Patients are strongly asked to take aspirin regularly and to avoid missing its dose.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION:

The result of the investigation shows that the first and second groups did not show a significant alteration in their CBC as well as hepatic tests and blood sugar, before, during and after treatment with aspirin. The third group, who was treated by 325mg/d for 5 months, had a significant alteration in CBC: anemia and leukocytosis (may be due decreased immune response linked to aging), decreased in plasma protein serum especially albumin (2 g/d compared to 3.5-5.0 g/d), and a slight elevation of SGPT (1 in contrast to 5 to 40 units/L) and SGOT (3 compared to 7-56 units/L). However, serum levels of ALP remain around its normal range (52 in contrast to 44 to 147 IU/L, indicating that extra or intrahepatic hepatic ducts have no obstruction, after excluding bone abnormalities. The unwanted effect may be linked to a high dose of aspirin as an antiaggregant and may be due to heart failure which is characterized by decreased hepatic blood flow.

Hypoglycemia was also noted in this group. Showing that aspirin (at 325mg/d) may have a negative effect on metabolic processes in the liver, namely decreased glycogenolysis as well as gluconeogenesis, these alterations appear only after 5 months of aspirin's therapy, along 3-4 months of treatment hepatic tests for all groups were around their ranges.

CONCLUSION:

Aspirin at doses of 75mg or 150mg/d causes no hepatocytes damage. Aspirin at doses of 75mg or 150 mg/d has no adverse effects on carbohydrate metabolism hence levels of sugar are still normal. Aspirin therapy is beneficial to reduce recurrence of IHD in all 3 groups for the first 4 months of

treatment. Aspirin with a dose of 325 causes hepatocytes injury, (elevation of hepatic enzymes and decreased albumin serum) and hypoglycemia especially with treatment greater than 5 months. CBC and hepatic tests, as well as blood sugar, must be investigated every 4 months in elderly patients receiving aspirin therapy for prophylaxis of IHD.

REFERENCES:

1. Raza A, Vierling J, Hussain KB. Genetics of drug-induced hepatotoxicity toxicity in Gilbert's syndrome. *Am J Gastroenterol* 2013; 108: 1936-7.
2. Whitten R, Milner DA Jr, Yeh MM, Kamiza S, Molyneux ME, Taylor TE. Liver pathology in Malawian children with fatal encephalopathy. *Hum Pathol*. 2011 Sep; 42 (9): 1230-9.
3. Feroz Z, Khan RA, Afroz S (2011). Cumulative toxicities on lipid profile and glucose following administration of antiepileptic, antihypertensive, antidiabetic and antiarrhythmic drugs. *Pak. J. Pharm. Sci.*, 24(1): 47-51.
4. Lee WM, Squires RH, Nyberg SL, et al. Acute liver failure: Summary of a workshop. *Hepatology*. 2008;47(4):1401-1415
5. Glasgow JF. Reye's syndrome: the case for a causal link with aspirin. *Drug Saf* 2006; 29: 1111-21.
6. Lacroix I, Lapeyre-Mestre M, Bagheri H, Pathak A, Montastruc JL; Club de Reflexion des cabinets de Groupe de Gastro-Enterologie (CREGG); General Practitioner Networks. Nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drug-induced liver injury: a case-control study in primary care. *Fundam Clin Pharmacol* 2004; 18: 201-6.
7. Lee WM. Drug-induced hepatotoxicity. *N Engl J Med*. 2003;349(5):474-485.
8. Carson, J.L., Strom, B.L., Duff, A. et al., Safety of nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs with respect to acute liver disease. *Arch Intern Med*. 1993;153:1331.
9. Lee W. Etiologies of acute liver failure. *Semin Liver Dis*. 2008;28(2):142-152.
10. Watkins PB, Seeff LB. Drug-induced liver injury: Summary of a single topic clinical research conference. *Hepatology*. 2006;43(3):618-631.
11. Zimmerman HJ. Effects of aspirin and acetaminophen on the liver. *Arch Intern Med*. 1981;141(3):331-342.
12. Sgro C, Clinard F, Ouazir K, et al. Incidence of drug-induced hepatic injuries: A French population-based study. *Hepatology*. 2002;36(2):451-455.
13. Zimmerman HJ. Drugs used to treat rheumatic and spastic muscle disease. Chapter 19: The

- NSAIDS. In Zimmerman, HJ. Hepatotoxicity: the adverse effects of drugs and other chemicals on the liver. 2nd ed. Philadelphia: Lippincott Williams & Williams, 1999, 599-602.
14. Silagy CA, McNeil JJ, Donnan GA, Tonkin AM, Worsam B, Champion K. Adverse effects of low dose aspirin in a healthy elderly population. *Clin Pharmacol Ther* 1993;54:84-9.
 15. Gurwitz JH, Gore JM, Goldberg RJ, Rubison M, Chandra N, Rogers WJ. Recent age-related trends in the use of thrombolytic therapy in patients who have had acute myocardial infarction. *Ann Intern Med* 1996;124:283-91
 16. Buerke M, Pittroff W, Meyer J, Darius H "Aspirin therapy: optimized platelet inhibition with different loading and maintenance doses." *Am Heart J* 130 (1995): 465-72
 17. Roderick PJ, Wilkes HC, Meade TW "The gastrointestinal toxicity of aspirin: an overview of randomized controlled trials." *Br J Clin Pharmacol* 35 (1993): 219-26
 18. Marks RD "Aspirin use and fecal occult blood testing." *Am J Med* 100 (1996): 596-7
 19. Russell AS, Sturge RA, Smith MA. Serum transaminases during salicylate therapy. *Br Med J* 1971; 2: 428-9.
 20. Bjorkman D (1998). Nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drug-associated toxicity of the liver, lower gastrointestinal tract, and esophagus. *The American Journal of Medicine*, 105(5)1: 17S-21S.
 21. Szykh TP, Efimova NIu. [Liver function in patients with aspirin-induced bronchial asthma] *Probl Tuberk* 1994; (4): 57-60.
 22. Prescott L (1980). Hepatotoxicity of mild analgesics. *British Journal of Clinical Pharmacology*, 10(2): 373-379.
 23. Wolfe JD, Metzger AL, & Goldstein RC (1974). Aspirin hepatitis. *Annals of internal medicine*, 80(1):74-76.